

Impact of Native Marketing on Customer Evaluation in Digital Media: A Study

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Abstract:- Native Marketing is mutely revolutionizing the dimensions of Digital Marketing and leading the world towards locating, enticing, and converting digital customers into business growth potential. This paper aims to focus on the aspect of Ascension in the Conceptual model of native marketing by testifying to the authentication of the Evaluation and Action stage of the Conceptual framework. An effort has been made to study the impact of native marketing on customer evaluation through primary research. The questionnaire tool was used to understand the impact native marketing has on evaluation criteria and the process of customers depending upon the product/service categories in digital media.

I. INTRODUCTION

In conjunction with the existing conventional advertising, the growth of internet activity and trade on the internet resulted in the emergence of a variety of new types of digital advertising. (De Haan et al., 2015). For the previous two decades, Digital advertising has been through a revolution (Tutaj Van Reijmersdal, 2012). Video broadcasts and remark for pay campaigns were by far the most common kinds of native advertising in the past. In the 1950s, they were largely broadcast on the radio. (Oliver, 2014). Video broadcasts and remark for pay campaigns were by far the most common kinds of native advertising in the past. In the 1950s, they were largely broadcast on the radio. (Stout, P. A., Wilcox, G. B., & Greer, L. S. 1989). But opposed to banner and display digital advertisements, native advertising is rapidly assuming the role of articles and generating considerably more influence and interaction. (Wojdowski, Bartosz W., and Nathaniel J. Evans, 2016). Because native advertising is a comparatively a recent phenomenon, there is still a paucity of knowledge about it, and therefore as a result, there seems to be no uniform definition. (IAB, 2013; Moore, 2014). Fundamentally, native advertising is described as a supported branding strategy that is shown on a projected display or inside a material feed, akin to literary information. (Vorkin .D, 2013).

II. CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF NATIVE ADVERTISING

The proposed conceptual framework of Native Marketing is classified into Five Aspects of

- Source
- Content
- Connect
- Ascension &
- Action

These Five Aspects are further segmented into another substructure or sub framework of Five Phases which are explained as underlying:

- **PHASE 1:** With the cooperation of the producer and the brand or sponsorship, they strive toward the inconspicuous display of the brand via content development and dissemination. The blended method is applied in this case, in which the product integrates with the material of the story/post on the website or webpage and motivates the viewer to contemplate or respond.
- **PHASE 2:** The product or information about the content is available and marketed to the client on the basis of twin concepts of Connect and Congruence, as mentioned earlier. Overall, the attraction of the topic contributes to the story's ability to stimulate people's attention. The 3 basic attractions in content creation are informative attractions, educative attention, and emotive language.
- **PHASE 3:** The narrative as well as its engagement are communicated through into the multimedia coverage, that in other ways can be generally classified into six primary communication categories: print media, tv broadcast, audiotapes, internet, open – air (Outdoor), and conventions.
- **PHASE 4:** After the narrative of the content is received by the marketing channels to the recipient, a connection is built by interaction and knowledge, awareness with the audience too.
- **PHASE 5:** This stage is with respect to ascension, that would mean to be the development of the consumer through awareness and level of knowledge existing at Top of the Funnel (ToFu) to assessment and evaluating and ultimately testing, unless the product significance seems to have adequate ability to encourage the client to traverse. (Gadiraju, 2019)

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of Native Marketing

(Gadiraju, 2019)

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Gadiraju, 2019)

The Study is a conceptual model of the framework of Native Advertisement which was understood through five major characteristics of Source, Content, Connect, Ascension and final Action. The first component, awareness, which includes source, content, and connect, has already been covered, while the following component, ascension, becomes the next natural step in customer advancement. The top, middle, and bottom tiers of the sales and marketing funnel correspond to awareness, evaluation, and conversion in the content life cycle model. The consumer is encouraged to progress to the next level of conversion by providing enough opportunities for brand evaluation through various engagement strategies. The ascension is the next phase, which proceeds to the customer's evaluation and, eventually, a test, and it is included in the structure to give the procedure a conclusion in the framework.

(Wojdyski et al., 2017)

Sponsorship transparency (ST), or the transparent communication of a persuasive message's sponsor, is essential for consumer preference and safety against deceptive advertising. This round of study, six stimulus examples had been selected, two from each of the categories of sponsored content, branded games, and online video advertising. A 12-item scale that is highly internally consistent and displays four linked internally consistent characteristics was constructed utilising an iterative item-generation procedure deeply grounded in consumer feedback and subjected to analysis and refinement using established procedures. Consumers' views of a message's ST

were shown to be influenced by various factors, including the message's brand presence, sponsor clarity, disclosure, and lack of deception. The findings confirmed that these elements are theoretically separate, despite their close relationship.

(Libert, 2015)

The most common challenge raised by executives who employ native advertising was one of scalability, particularly if they want to appeal to a wider of publications and viewers. Many businesses today depend on content marketing and native advertising to raise brand awareness and almost 70% of the consumers love to study about things through content rather than traditional or TV advertisements. Over 30 content marketing agencies were surveyed to discuss content types and the analytics they employ to monitor ROI. The price range of \$5,000-\$50,000 was shown to be associated with campaigns that generated the most links, implying that agencies were able to create innovative, larger-scale initiatives, influencer marketing, and content amplification instead of sending press statements.

(Taylor, 2017)

In native advertising, the terms "advertising" or "sponsored" are more successful if they are in the centre or bottom of the ad. The Marketing Family's Black Sheep In recent years, "native advertising" has become part of a growing income model for print media, driven mainly by challenges created by decreased advertising money and declining distribution. Product placement is different from native advertising in that the viewer is consuming a product (e.g., a film or tv programme) meant to entertain wherein the placement is part of a story — and will not take the

particular form and visual appeal of editorials of the publishing company.

(New Survey: 5 Facts, 2016)

Within the study, 48 percent of media news organizations are now using native advertising, while 39 percent are expected to use it in the future, and a whopping 89 percent see native advertising as being very essential or crucial to their business. The most prevalent method of measurement is still traffic. When that relates to native advertising, dwell period, time invested, and audience interactions are all essential metrics, but traffic has always been the most significant, with 60% of news media executives reporting this is how they measure native advertising. This may not be the case that the customer is correct. The largest problem for native advertising, according to 46% of news media publishers polled, is presenting native advertising to sponsors.

(Gadiraju, 2018)

Numerous native advertisements try to target pertinent consumer groups and trying to engage them in multiple levels of engagement with brands, enabling them the background knowledge, such that people gradually and also very seamlessly graduate from the top of the funnel (TOFu) - awareness, to the middle and lower levels of assessment and tests. Because of the in-stream essence and intricacy of native advertising, there has been some debate about the principles of its use, as many brands are hesitant to disclose sponsored posts for fear of customer blowback.

(Kim et al., 2018)

Because sponsored advertorials ads imitate a publication's genre and start competing with banner advertisements on a media site, two aspects were considered: advertisement type (native vs. banner) and placement type (solo vs. pair). On all response variable, there was interaction effect impacts among both the advertisement forms and placement type, with native advertising displaying a significant reduction in duo vs. solo placement. On all response variable, there was interaction effect impacts among both the advertisement forms and placement type, with native advertising displaying a significant reduction in duo vs. solo placement. Consumers' assessment of native advertising in duo placement was reduced when it was paired alongside banner advertising. It's the first theoretically and empirically analysis of the impact of media contexts on consumer responses to native advertising in online news media environments.

(Wojdyski & Evans, 2019)

The research believes that advertising acknowledgement is conceptually defined as a dependant variable which attempts to measure the initialization or dearth of implementation of an advertising framework prior to the expiry of processing of information due to the sheer role that the framework plays in shaping how consumers perceives and analyse advertisements. Because advertising acknowledgement is so important in shaping covert brand equity, scholars must know the process underpinning advertising acknowledgement and accurately

measure when advertising awareness occurs. Provided that the design, appearance, and placement of native and covert advertising execution time can vary greatly. The significant proportion of customer study in the area of native and covert advertising has concentrated on the impact of reporting attributes on top-down advertising acknowledgement. future research could use the proposed model to identify, implement, and test specific, non-disclosure related elements considered to induce bottom-up advertising acknowledgement.

(Jung & Heo, 2019)

The study looked at how ad disclosure and ad recognition anticipate native marketing effectiveness in connection to cognitive strategies. Two different experimental research indicate that understanding of social media advertising techniques and advertisement awareness, instead of the specificity of ad disclosing, impacted assessment of a natively structured format ad. The results indicate that previous experience with social media ads, instead of ad disclosure, provoked acknowledgement of the natively formatted ad. Such results also reveal that ad disclosure has minimal effect and highlight the value of educating consumers. The study discovered that expertise of Digital marketing impacted native ad evaluation. Rather than the focus on the main ad verification phrasing, strategies and ad acknowledgement are used. The study proved that ad recognition made people wary of a covert persuasion effort and only after people were extremely motivated did acknowledgment play a significant role in provoking defensive reactions aware.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH

To Validate the Phase5 of Native Marketing -Conceptual Model. (Gadiraju, 2019)

- To testify the authentication of the Evaluation and Action stage of the Conceptual Framework.

V. HYPOTHESIS

- Null Hypothesis:
- Native Advertising impacts evaluation criteria and process of customers depending upon the product/service categories in digital platforms.
- Native Advertising does not have any significant impact on customers depending upon the product/service categories in digital platforms.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is exploratory in nature, wherein the unknown is derived from the known knowledge through a questionnaire i.e., Primary Data is collected to validate Phase 5 of the Conceptual Model- Native Marketing, and secondary data is thoroughly studied to draw inferences from it.

- Scope:
 - The research is conducted within the Business School i.e., Universal Business School, it is inclusive of all races, genders, and ages.
 - The view of various sections of the Indian society is taken into consideration while testifying the

authentication of the Evaluation and Action stage of the Conceptual Framework.

- The sample size of this research is finite to 50 respondents.

VII. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The questionnaire is the primary research tool utilized in the research paper to obtain research findings. The Questionnaire is made through the medium of a google form containing a set of Six questions that was sent to the respondents. An article on basic understanding of life insurance investments and other ways to invest, which was actually a native marketing technique used by SBI Life Insurance as a partnership, was sent to the respondents before the questionnaire was actually sent so that they could answer the Questionnaire with greater understanding and

perception. The respondents should be able to detect the partnership and subsequently accept the Sponsor brand, which in this case is SBI Life Insurance. This is where native marketing plays its role in this research paper.

From the Primary research, it can be deduced that without the brand’s appearance directly into digital media the respondents are receiving awareness about life insurance in this case and are evaluating their options and then trying it out. The Responses clearly have shown that native marketing has silently marketed its way to customers through partnered or sponsored advertisement i.e., the article in this case. 70% of the respondent after reading the article didn’t recognize that the article was sponsored by SBI Life and once the respondent recognized the brand, they trusted it straight away because of its general information on investments and life insurance.

Did you know that the above article was a partnered advertisement with SBI Life Insurance
53 responses

Fig. 2: Response for Partnership with SBI Life Insurance

How would you rate SBI Life Insurance in terms of a trustworthy Investment option.
53 responses

Fig. 3: Trustworthiness of SBI Life Insurance as an Investment

On a scale of 1-5 where 1 being worst and 5 being best when the question was asked about “How would you rate SBI Life Insurance in terms of a trustworthy Investment option?”, 50% of the respondents gave it a **4 rating** and 28% of the respondents gave it a **5 rating**. This proves that the hypothesis i.e., “**Native Advertising impacts evaluation criteria and process of customers depending upon the product/service categories in digital platforms**” is **True**.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

- The primary data collection is restricted to the business School i.e., Universal Business School and it's quite a small demographic size.
- From the primary Data we can clearly see that the respondents to the questionnaire are predominantly between the age of 20-25 yrs.
- The study is limited to 50 respondents.
- This study takes only the digital media aspect into consideration.
- The personal bias of respondents may have an impact on the ultimate results of the research.

IX. CONCLUSION

There seems to be no uncertainty about how native advertising would shape the times ahead of us which will be dominated by the interests of digital advertising since interacting and urging the viewers to react with real and honest enlightening appealing will shine out when contrasted to forceful ads which put deviate the consumers' attention at the same time. The challenge is to recognize the approach and attempt to ablate people forward into a healthful and instructive marketing strategy that rests its presentation on real facts, instead of clogging buyers' heads and pushing a brand. Hence the requirement for more study on the influence of native advertising on buyer behavior, and the formulation of clear laws governing specific uncertain sectors such as the declaration of sponsorship, and so on. Lastly, it's indeed clear that native advertisements are to control and dominate articles, and digital media, and the list follows and enhances content marketing in terms of content creation and brand recognition. The personality linked with them is matched by the unspoken moral principles of reporting the data in its circumstantial importance.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] Wojdyski, B., Evans, N., & Hoy, M. (2017). Measuring Sponsorship Transparency in the Age of Native Advertising. *Journal Of Consumer Affairs*, 52(1), 115-137. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joca.12144>
- [2.] Taylor, C. (2017). Native Advertising: The Black Sheep of the Marketing Family. *International Journal Of Advertising*, 36(2), 207-209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2017.1285389>
- [3.] Libert, k. (2015). Comparing the ROI of Content Marketing and Native Advertising. *Harvard Business Publishing*.
- [4.] New Survey: 5 Facts About Native Advertising and the News Media Industry. (2016). [Blog]. Retrieved 28 February 2022, from <https://blog.nativeadvertisinginstitute.com/new-survey-5-facts-native-advertising-news-media-industry>.
- [5.] Gadiraju, D. (2018). NATIVE ADVERTISING-THE FUTURE OF CONTENT MARKETING AND ONLINE ADVERTISING. *Journal Of Emerging Technologies And Innovative Research*, 5(5). Retrieved 28 February 2022, from <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1805137.pdf>.
- [6.] Gadiraju, D. (2019). NATIVE ADVERTISING-A CONCEPTUAL MODEL. *International Journal Of Research And Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 6(1). Retrieved from <https://www.ijrar.org/papers/IJRAR19J3485.pdf>
- [7.] Kim, S., Youn, S., & Yoon, D. (2018). Consumers' responses to native vs. banner advertising: moderation of persuasion knowledge on interaction effects of ad type and placement type. *International Journal Of Advertising*, 38(2), 207-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2018.1451208>
- [8.] Wojdyski, B., & Evans, N. (2019). The Covert Advertising Recognition and Effects (CARE) model: Processes of persuasion in native advertising and other masked formats. *International Journal Of Advertising*, 39(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2019.1658438>
- [9.] Jung, A., & Heo, J. (2019). Ad Disclosure vs. Ad Recognition: How Persuasion Knowledge Influences Native Advertising Evaluation. *Journal Of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2018.1520661>
- [10.] Amazeen, M. (2021). Native Advertising in a Mobile Era: Effects of Ability and Motivation on Recognition in Digital News Contexts. *Digital Journalism*, 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2020.1860783>
- [11.] Tutaj, Karolina & Reijmersdal, Eva. (2012). Effects of online advertising format and persuasion knowledge on audience reactions. *Journal of Marketing Communications*. 18. 5-18. [10.1080/13527266.2011.620765](https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2011.620765).
- [12.] De Haan, E., Wiesel, T. & Pauwels, K. (2015), “The effectiveness of different forms of online advertising for purchase conversion in a multiple-channel attribution framework”, *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Nov. 2014, p. 1-17.

- [13.] Oliver, J. (2014). Native Advertising. Last Week Tonight with John Oliver: HBO
- [14.] Stout, P. A., Wilcox, G. B., & Greer, L. S. (1989). Trends in magazine advertorial use, *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 66(4), 960-964.
- Probst, Florian, Laura Grosswiele, and Regina Pflieger (2013), "Who Will Lead and Who Will Follow: Identifying Influential Users in [24] Online Social Networks: A Critical Review and Future Research Directions," *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 5 (3), 179–93.
- [15.] Moore, J. D. 2014), "New Goes Native: An Examination of Online Media's Disclosure Practices for Sponsored Content", University of Nebraska, Lincoln, Nebraska
- [16.] Interactive Advertising Bureau, (2013), "The Native Advertising Playbook" [online] Available at: <http://www.iab.com/guidelines/native-advertising>
- [17.] Dvorkin, L. (2013), "Inside Forbes: What next for Native Ads? Controversy gives way to market realities", [online] Available at: <http://www.forbes.com/sites/lewisdvorkin/2013/07/08/inside-forbes-whats-next-for-native-ads-controversy-gives-way-to-marketrealities>